

The Smart University as an Entry to Developing Higher Education. A Review

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Abstract

The higher education sector is undergoing a fundamental transformation in light of rapid technological developments, leading to the emergence of the concept of the smart university as an integrated educational model that employs the latest digital technologies to support the educational and administrative processes. This research aims to explore the role of smart universities in developing higher education by analyzing the dimensions of this concept and its importance in enhancing the quality of education and creating interactive and sustainable learning environments. The study concludes that smart universities contribute to raising the competitiveness of higher education institutions by adopting modern strategies that support innovation, achieve sustainability, and improve educational services. The study recommends strengthening universities' digital infrastructure and developing integrated policies and strategies to support the transition to a smart model, ensuring a positive impact on students, faculty members, and university administration.

Keywords: *smart universities, higher education, digital transformation, artificial intelligence, cloud computing, interactive learning environments.*

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Introduction

With the technological development and its reflection on the creation of new types of education such as e-learning and virtual education, this type of university came as a result of the expansion in the use of technology in education. The main goal of transforming universities into smart universities is to have a leading university in education or research, and not to focus only on buildings and their equipment (Al-Awini, 2016). Smart universities aim to make the educational process more dynamic and effective, transforming the student from a consumer of knowledge to a producer of it, and transforming society as a whole into a knowledge society (Bakro, 2017). Technology and the Internet have become an approach followed in all aspects of life, as technology is one of the many variables that must be taken into account due to its importance in the development and progress of individuals' lives due to its direct impact on their lives. Specific trends

in laws and policies have become linked to the analysis of the economy and market that affects university learning environments and their operations. In addition, social issues, modern innovations, and technology have led to changing the way people learn (Al-Awini, 2016). These changes are reflected in university institutions, which are required to provide high-quality services in order to maintain their competitiveness, to make many adjustments in teaching patterns and methods, and to move towards e-learning.

The concept of Smart Universities

Universities are considered scientific innovation institutions and a fundamental means for the advancement and development of societies. Universities are the vanguard of any society striving for progress. They have profound influences on their societies, as they lead the processes of development and change. Therefore, they cannot be transformed into rigid organizations, but rather must be characterized by continuous development, modernization, and improvement in order to renew their roles or increase the effectiveness of their contributions to serving society, in addition to cognitive development (Awf, Mustafa, Al-Mallah, 2020). Smart universities are a natural and logical evolution of e-learning, accompanied by the widespread adoption of open-source cloud computing and educational platforms, which have become one of the most important pillars of modern university education (Jawad, Abboudi, & Mahmud, 2018). By reviewing numerous references and sources related to smart universities, we found that researchers and scholars disagree on defining the concept of smart universities, given that this is a modern topic. There are several definitions that describe the smart university, which was primarily inspired by the design of smart cities. Among the most important of these definitions are the following: Colleen & Vladimir (2018) defined it as a place that provides essential data to drive, analyze, and improve the educational environment through sensor data, using data linkage and making it open, while formalizing education. Uskov et al. (2018) defined it as a modern and rapidly growing university that represents the creative integration of smart technology, smart features, smart software, smart systems, smart devices, smart education, smart curricula, academic analytics, and various computer applications. The researchers conclude that the characteristics of smart universities are summarized in their being highly efficient universities, using the latest developments in information technology and communications technology, and working to provide a range of services available via the Internet, as they work to provide rich, interactive and constantly changing educational environments, by empowering the capabilities of individuals (students, faculty members, administration, visitors) and their behaviors and encouraging them to interact and cooperate continuously, in addition to their interest in increasing participation between students and faculty members, and increasing cooperation between them within a framework that makes them participants and responsible in developing and raising the level of the educational process, and to achieve the common goal of learning in a better way.

Literature Review

A study by Dong et al. (2020) titled "Smart Campus: Definition, Framework, Technologies, and Services" highlights a multidisciplinary perspective on the smart campus. Based on a comprehensive review of supporting technologies and current smart campus proposals, a human-centered, learning-oriented smart campus is conceptualized, defined, and framed, primarily aiming to meet stakeholder interests and enhance educational performance in the context of technological advancements. It also discusses the multidisciplinary factors that either enhance or constrain the smart campus revolution. This study also aims to provide a reference for the smart campus for

international education providers, governments, and technology companies that offer such services. The study arrives at a clear concept of the smart campus, clearly identifying the elements of smart universities, including individuals, technology, the learning environment, e-learning, and knowledge. The study also highlights the direct role of smart universities in achieving sustainability and energy conservation in various aspects, creating an interactive teaching and learning environment that positively impacts student achievement, and creating an attractive environment for academic staff in universities that rely on smart education systems. A study (Nisar & Prabhakar & Strakova, 2019) titled “Social Media: Benefits of Information, Knowledge Management, and Smart Organizations” aimed to investigate the growth of social media within organizations and the effective means social technologies provide for organizations to manage their information flows and thus bring about changes in their knowledge management systems, which can then be linked to performance improvements. Knowledge management tools enable employees to participate in information exchange and communication. To achieve the study objective, content analysis was used, across two variables: information richness and informal communication, to measure their impact on organizational productivity. The study results showed a positive impact of knowledge management discussion groups (KMDGs) on organizational performance through embedded information and social communication and their contribution to achieving smart organization.

Conclusion

Based on the researchers' findings, conclusions, and review of previous studies, and in order for this research paper to fulfill its role and achieve its objectives in the best possible way, some proposals must be presented, as follows: 1- Work to provide modern, wide-range communications devices based on smart technologies in all university facilities. 2- The necessity of reconsidering, maintaining, and developing the university campus buildings in a dynamic and technologically advanced manner, making them more capable of serving the smart educational process. University buildings should include smart operating and sensing systems (energy, alarm, protection), in addition to the necessity of working to air-condition university buildings in an energy-saving manner, i.e., moving towards adopting environmentally friendly energy systems. 3- Continuously work to support the creative capabilities of faculty members, making them more capable of keeping pace with technological developments related to the educational process. 4- Formulating clear strategies for leveraging the concept of smart universities to improve the university's institutional performance and its public image locally and internationally, and to make it more in line with scientific and technological developments. 5- Increasing attention to providing a smart work environment to contribute to the comfort of university employees. 6- Working to provide modern tools and technologies to extract, collect, and update knowledge from diverse sources, providing advanced technological applications and tools to handle the growing data and information, and developing a unified database and continuously updating it to keep pace with rapid technological changes. 7- Supporting efforts to provide a green environment (technology, buildings, facilities) within the university.

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